

Educational consequences of the changing landscape of searching

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1. Introduction

An important aspect of search and search engines in society is how to develop young people's abilities and critical understanding of these tools in education—that is, their information literacy. The panel therefore aims to develop the understanding of search in education in a changing digital landscape. The narrative of a 'digital generation' has been challenged by empirical research over the years, including in relation to search and search engines (e.g., Hargittai et al., 2010; Sundin & Carlsson, 2016) and in general terms of a critical understanding of datafication in society (Pangrazio & Selwyn, 2021). While the topic of evaluating information has received attention in the schools of many countries (e.g. Wineburg & McGrew, 2016), the practice of finding information is often overlooked (Limberg et al., 2008; Haider & Sundin, 2019).

The panel takes as its starting point in three challenges for the role of search in education. The first challenge concerns the increasing diffusion of generative AI into the information infrastructure, resulting in sources no longer being visible to the user, or at least less so (Sundin, 2025). Applications of generative AI and the increasing inclusion of Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) technology by search engines run the risk of promoting an understanding of the search engine as a machine producing neutral facts. The second challenge concerns the trend of young people turning to social media and video platforms instead of using general web search engines (Pires et al., 2021) complicating matters further by diffusing epistemic authority and credibility frameworks into and across opaque as well as algorithmically and socially influenced platforms and networks. The third challenge concerns how many countries are experiencing a shift in education policy, with so-called knowledge-based curricula gaining ground at the expense of pupils' curiosity and independent learning (Buckingham, 2017).

In four different cases, the panelists reflect on these aspects when discussing search and search engines as a content in schools.

1.1. Case 1: Current debates on the role of search and digital competence in Sweden

Anna-Lena Godhe has done extensive research in classrooms, often working in collaboration with teachers, focusing on how the digitalisation of society and school affects subjects, teachers, and students. In the panel, she will focus on searching and digital competence which is the concept currently used in Swedish curricula to address what students should learn throughout compulsory school. However, the concept of digital competence and thereby the different aspects of it is currently being questioned in political and media debates in Sweden. Her presentation will attend to how searching is addressed in this changing landscape, possible outcomes and consequences for Swedish teachers and students.

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1.2. Case 2: Young peoples' searching in social media and algorithmic awareness

As part of Amanda Persson's ongoing PhD research on young cis men's encounters with the manosphere, she explores how young people search for information in a digital infrastructure that is largely characterised by algorithms. Her findings show that rather than following linear models of information seeking, young users move fluidly across platforms — liking, scrolling, sharing, muting and reporting content in ways that are both expressive and identity-forming. Persson will discuss the tensions between the way information searching and source evaluation is taught in formal education and the way it is lived by young people. She put forward the question: How can we better align information literacy education with the complex, emotional, and social realities of young people's daily information activities?

1.3. Case 3: Searching as a performatively entangled activity within the double bind of the school

Jan Ole Størup has qualitatively explored the collaborative information practices of Danish lower secondary school students during project work as part of his PhD project. In the panel, he will delve into how students' search, evaluation, and use of information are socially, discursively, and performatively entangled activities that are seldomly allowed to unfold through curiosity, wonder, or exploration alone due to an education system in which students are often led to focus on outcome rather than process. This creates a paradoxical situation placing students in a double bind through being expected to critically seek and examine information on the one hand, while also having to pursue educational measures of success such as good grades and teacher recognition on the other. Regarding students' development of information literacies in school, this raises the question: What are students actually learning?

1.4. Case 4: From sources to answers and consequences for information literacy

Olof Sundin has many years of experience in researching search engines, search and media and information literacy. In the panel, he will discuss how an increasingly AI-infused information infrastructure renders sources less visible to users in the context of search. He will address the increasingly blurred distinction between searching for documents and looking for an answer. When suggestions such as 'Don't Google it, Just Grook it' (TOI World Desk, 2025) as a basis for checking the accuracy of information online, that will have broader implications the growing invisibility of sources holds for media and information literacy.

1.5. Format

The panel discussion is designed for 90 minutes, and it will consist of a combination of short case presentations by the four panellists and a broader discussion to which the audience is invited. The panellists are both young and experienced researchers.

5 minutes for introduction: A brief introduction to explain the background and the purpose of the panel.

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8-10 minutes for case presentations: the presentations will take a starting point in each panellist's research and revolve around the question, what are the most salient challenges in the changing landscape of searching for formal education?

30 minutes for a general discussion: The discussion will take place among the panellists as well as with and between the participants in the audience, who will be asked to bring their own research experience as well as insights in the curriculum in different countries.

10 minutes for closing remarks: Each panellist summarises the discussion from their research perspective and gives an outlook on what the discussion can mean for their future research.

2. Acknowledgements

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